

CERTAINTY BSC's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for ESM and observational data created at the BSC is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

CERTAINTY

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Organizations

Technical University of Catalonia, Barcelona Supercomputing
Center, Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY BSC's DMP

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: CERTAINTY

Project: CERTAINTY

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Modeling data from EC-Earth

Model outputs fields related to experiments on aerosols and climate

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://ec-earth.org>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Project partners.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

https://cmor.llnl.gov/mydoc_cmor3_CV/

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ESGF data node

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

TBD

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Collaboration with other Projects

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. María Gonçalves Ageitos (orcid:0000-0003-3857-6403)
- b. Carlos Pérez García-Pando (orcid:0000-0002-4456-0697)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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